

Effect of Hybrid Fibers on Water absorption and Mechanical Strengths of Geopolymer Concrete based on Blast Furnace Slag

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, geopolymers, as a new class of green cement binders, have gained significant attention as an environmental-friendly alternative to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) which can potentially reduce negative environmental impacts of OPC. Fiber Reinforced Geopolymer Concrete (FRGPC) is known as a new type of concrete with enhanced ductility characteristics over conventional concrete. In this experimental study, hybrid fibers of 12mm modified polypropylene and 55mm polyolefin were used to manufacture FRGPC specimens based on Granulated Ground Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS). In this regard, FRGPC and non-fiber specimens were produced. The specimens were subjected to compressive, indirect tensile and 3-point flexural tests, as well as water absorption capacity and specific density studies. The obtained results showed that using hybrid fibers decreased the specific density and water absorption, a slight increase in compressive strength and a significant improvement in tensile and flexural strengths of FRGPC specimens compared to non-fiber specimens.

Keyword: Fiber Reinforced Geopolymer Concrete, Hybrid Fibers, Compressive Strength, Tensile Strength, Flexural Strength

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) as the main constituent of conventional concrete is the most widely used cementitious material in the construction industry [1-4]. Portland cement production has major environmental disadvantages, including high energy consumption, natural resources exhaustion and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions [1,5]. Production of 1 ton of OPC releases approximately 1 ton of CO₂ into the environment [6-8] and consumes 1.5 tons of raw materials [9]. On the other hand, pollution and global warming phenomenon have become a major concern in developed countries [2]. Global warming is caused by the emission of greenhouse gases and among the greenhouse gases, CO₂ plays a major role in global warming with a 60% share [10]. The production process of OPC is accounted for 7 to 10% of global CO₂ emissions [11]. Our country (Iran), as the fifth largest producer of OPC worldwide, is

also exposed to these environmental problems. In recent years, geopolymers have been introduced as a new cementitious material and green alternative to OPC. Geopolymers were first developed by Davidovits, as a new family of binders of inorganic origin. Usage of geopolymer cements can reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 44-64% compared to Portland cement [12]. It also improves waste management which has a positive impact on the environment [13]. Regarding civil engineering applications, Geopolymer Concrete (GPC) has showed enhanced physical and mechanical properties over conventional concrete, e.g. higher mechanical strength [14-16], enhanced durability [17], higher resistance to elevated temperatures and fire [18-20], lower permeability, improved resistance to solvents and acids [21,22] and lower creep effects [23,24]. Geopolymers are inorganic alumino-silicate materials produced from raw

materials, rich in silica (SiO₂) and alumina (Al₂O₃), in combination with an alkaline activator solution [25,26]. The geopolymerization process involves a substantially fast chemical reaction under alkaline condition on Si-Al minerals, that results in a three-dimensional polymeric chain and ring structure consisting of Si-O-Al bonds [27-29]. Davidovits utilized the name “Poly(sialate)” to indicate the chemical composition of geopolymers, in which “Poly” represented the polymeric nature, and “sialate” was an abbreviation for the silicon-oxo-aluminate chain. He has also distinguished 3 types of monomers that form the basis of the geopolymer structure: the Poly(sialate) type (PS), the Poly(sialate-siloxo) type (PSS) and the Poly(sialate-disiloxo) type (PSDS) [31,32]. The alkaline activator solution is one of the two main constituents of geopolymers, playing a significant role in the formation of Al and Si crystals, and is normally chosen based on Na and K (solvent alkali metals) solutions. The most convenient alkali solution used in geopolymerization is a compound solution of NaOH or KOH and Na₂SiO₃ or K₂SiO₃ [32]. The aluminosilicate source, also known by other names such as raw material, geopolymerization source and source material, plays the most important role in geopolymer cements, as the supplier of Si and Al. The raw material, depending on required characteristics, cost and availability, can be of natural origin (e.g. zeolite), synthetic (e.g. metakaolin) or waste materials (e.g. fly ash or Granulated Ground Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS)). As aforementioned, concrete, and especially GPC, has many advantages but the disadvantages of concrete also have to be considered. Low tensile strength and consequent low ductility and high brittleness, is of the major disadvantages of concrete. Introduction of fibers in the concrete mix is a solution developed in the past decades to overcome this issue. Usage of fibers to enhance brittle composites dates back to 3500 years ago when straw-reinforced sun-dried bricks were used to build the 57-meter-high hill of Aqar Quf near Baghdad [33]. Horse tail hair is also used to reinforce mortar and plaster [34]. Application of different types and geometries of fibers in concrete, “Fiber Reinforced Concrete (FRC)”, has shown to effectively control crack propagation and improve physical and mechanical properties of the concrete composite, e.g. tensile strength [35]. Nowadays, fibers are widely used to improve a variety of properties such as: compressive, flexural and tensile strengths, resistance to impact and extreme temperatures, etc. in different types of concrete. These fibers range from metallic to polymeric fibers but research on concrete reinforced with polymer-based fiber types, due to their economic benefit over steel fibers, is high on the agenda. Polyolefin is a relatively new type of polymer-based fiber. These fibers are used to make elasto-plastic concrete which has shown to increase flexural toughness, fatigue strength and impact resistance and reduce crack propagation in concrete composites [36]. On the other hand, in recent years, application of 2-part and multipart hybrid fibers to enhance various

properties of the concrete composite has gained significant interest. Fiber Reinforced Geopolymer Concrete (FRGPC) is a new type of concrete with higher ductility than conventional concrete [37] and has been the subject of many recent studies to investigate its potential pros and cons. Gao et al [38] conducted research on GPC reinforced with 6 and 12mm long steel fibers and showed that the shorter fiber is more effective in controlling micro cracks, while the longer fiber provides ductility at extensive cracking scenarios. Furthermore, a hybrid fiber configuration showed to yield optimal crack-control features and prevents cracking in both macro and micro phases. Asrani et al [39] investigated slag-based FRGPC using Polypropylene or PP (13 mm long), glass (15 mm long) and 3D-steel (60 mm long) fibers of 0.3, 0.3 and 1.6 % volume content, respectively, and as single and hybrid fiber GPC configurations. The results showed that incorporating only PP fiber results in a significant increase (about 108%) of flexural strength over plain GPC. Hybridization showed to further improve strength characteristics, e.g. a hybrid PP and steel FRGPC composite displayed 30 and 200 % growth in compressive and flexural strength over plain GPC, respectively. Alberti et al [40] studied the properties of Polyolefin fiber-reinforced concrete enhanced with steel fibers in low ratios and concluded that the use of polyolefin fibers improves mechanical strength and provides considerable ductility and flexural toughness. Han et al [41] investigated the effect of Polyolefin fibers on the specifications of concrete containing silica fume. The results showed that using these fibers resulted in a 13% increase in flexural strength as well as a 70% decrease in crack propagation. Additionally, the specimens containing Polyolefin fibers exhibited 2 times higher impact resistance than those containing steel fibers and 14 times more than the control (no fiber) specimens. Deng et al [42] also studied the effect of macro-Polyolefin fibers on the concrete properties. The researchers observed the positive effects of Polyolefin fibers in preventing crack propagation by increasing the fiber content. Celik et al [36] studied the effect of different fiber types for FRGPC, on its resistance to elevated temperatures. Polyolefin, Basalt, Modified Polyamide and PVA fibers and incorporated as non-hybrid composites were considered. The results showed that the use of Polyolefin fibers at the optimum percentage (i.e. 1.2%) increased compressive strength by 4.7% and flexural strength by 25% compared to the control (non-fiber) specimen. In this experimental study, new types of hybrid polymer fibers, including: long twist Polyolefin fibers and short modified Polypropylene fibers, was used to manufacture FRGPC composites. After conducting initial tests to achieve the final mix design of the GGBFS-based geopolymer concrete, the effect of hybrid Polyolefin fibers on water absorption capacity, specific density and compressive, tensile and flexural strengths of FRGPC, were studied. In this regard, FRGPC and non-fiber specimens were produced. Thereafter, the specimens were subjected to the

compressive, indirect tensile and 3-point flexural strength tests as well as water absorption capacity and specific

density investigations. Finally, the obtained experimental results were collected, analyzed and reported.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

The X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) chemical analysis of the GGBFS used in this study is given in [Table 1](#). NaOH with 98% purity and liquid Na₂SiO₃ with SiO₂/Na₂O molar ratio of 2, were used to prepare the alkaline activator

solution. [Table 2](#) represents the chemical analysis of the Na₂SiO₃, NaOH, and KOH substances.

Table 1: XRF chemical analysis of GGBFS

Chemical substance	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	MnO	SO ₃	Cl	LOI
Weight %	34.4	11.2	37.2	0.6	0.62	0.68	9.8	1.58	1.2	0.02	0.5

Table 2: Chemical analysis of NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ solutions

NaOH			Na ₂ SiO ₃		
Chemical substance	Result	Unit	Chemical substance	Result	Unit
NaOH	98	%	SiO ₂	30	%
Na ₂ CO ₃	1	%	Na ₂ O	14.5	%
NaCl	200	ppm	Water	55.5	%
Fe	6	ppm			
SiO ₂	15.7	ppm			
Appearance	White flake		Appearance	Clear liquid	

The aggregates were obtained from quarries around Tehran. Aggregates with granular sizes of 7-10 mm was used as coarse aggregate (sand), and < 4 mm sized aggregates were used as fine aggregate. Fine and coarse aggregates were sieved according to ASTM C33 [43]. The fineness modulus (using ASTM C136 [44]) and sand equivalent (using ASTM D2419 [45]) values of the fine

aggregates were measured equal to 3.01 and 73, respectively. To reduce water content and improve workability of concrete, polycarboxylate-based Super Plasticizer (SP) was incorporated. The fibers used in this study was obtained from Nanonakh Sirjan Company. The main properties of the fibers are presented in [Table 3](#) and [Figure 1](#) displays the fibers used in this study.

Figure 1: Image of fibers used in this study

Table 3: Properties of fibers

Properties	Hybrid fibers
Length (mm)	12,55
Density (gr/cm ³)	0.91-0.95
Tensile strength (MPa)	350-750
Module of elasticity (GPa)	4.5
Water absorbency	No
Alkaline and acid resistant	Excellent
Melting point (°C)	165

2.2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

In this part, 5 mix designs were defined, as illustrated in [Table 4](#). To optimize the fiber volume content, different values of fiber volume content were added to the GPC specimens: 0.15%, 0.2% and 0.25%. Initially, the alkaline activator solution, constituting of NaOH (14M), Na₂SiO₃, SP and the extra water (according to each mix design) are combined and allowed to cool for 24 hrs. In the mixing process, the aggregates, GGBFS and fibers were first dry mixed in the mixer for 3 minutes. Next, the alkaline activator solution was added and the concrete was mixed for a further 2 minutes. Subsequently,

compressive (100x100x100 mm cubes), tensile (200x100 mm cylinders) and flexural (100x100x500 mm beams) specimens were molded and vibrated for 10 seconds on a vibrating table. The specimens were cured in the oven (90 °C) for 24hrs. After the curing process, the specimens were allowed to rest at laboratory ambient temperature. The specimens were subjected to the 7- and 28-day compressive, tensile (Brazilian) and 3-point flexural strength tests, as well as water absorption capacity and specific density tests.

Table 4: Fiber Reinforced GPC mix designs

Mix ID	GGBFS (Kg/m ³)	NaOH (Kg/m ³)	Na ₂ SiO ₃ (Kg/m ³)	Coarse aggregates (Kg/m ³)	Fine aggregates (Kg/m ³)	SP (Kg/m ³)	Extra water (Kg/m ³)	Fiber content (%)
Control	400	80	120	840	840	8	10	0
F-0.15	400	80	120	840	840	8	10	0.15
F-0.2	400	80	120	840	840	8	10	0.2
F-0.25	400	80	120	840	840	8	10	0.25

The various tests were conducted according to standard testing procedures: compressive strength test according to the BS1881: Part116 [\[46\]](#), indirect tensile strength test according to ASTM C496 [\[47\]](#), 3-point flexural strength

test according to ASTM C293 [\[48\]](#) and ASTM C1018 [\[49\]](#), water absorption capacity and specific density tests according to ASTM C642 [\[50\]](#).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. WATER ABSORPTION AND SPECIFIC DENSITY

[Figures 2](#) and [3](#) display the specific density and water

absorption capacity of the FRGPC and unreinforced GPC specimens, respectively.

Figure 2: Specific density of the FRGPC and control specimens

Figure 3: Water absorption of the FRGPC and control specimens

The specific density of the control specimen (unreinforced GPC) is calculated equal to 2338 kg/m^3 . Usage of fibers in the GPC shows to reduce specific density with fiber volume content. Also, increasing the fiber content resulted in a further reduction in the specific density of the specimens, so that in the FRGPC containing 0.25% fibers, almost 3% of the specific density was reduced. This can be explained to the lower specific density of the fibers compared to the GPC matrix. The specific density of the fibers used is in the range of $0.91\text{-}0.95 \text{ gr/cm}^3$ (equivalent to $910\text{-}950 \text{ kg/m}^3$), thus reducing

the specific density of the FRGPC specimens compared to the control specimen. The water absorption capacity of the control specimen is around 4.3%. Water absorption capacity of the FRGPC composites reduces with fiber content. The random dispersion of the micro and macro size fibers allow them to stitch micro cracks and prevent development of new ones in the geopolymer matrix. This mechanism results in the higher density of the geopolymeric matrix structure and consequent reduction in water absorption capacity [51].

3.2. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

The 7- and 28-day compressive strengths of the FRGPC composites are illustrated in Figure 4. The 7 and 28-day compressive strengths of the control specimen was 95.5 and 101 MPa, respectively. In the hybrid FRGPC composites, 0.15, 0.2 and 0.25% fiber content resulted in approximately 2.2, 6 and 3.4% improvement in compressive strengths compared to the control specimen, respectively. This issue may be due to the reinforcement of the concrete matrix by hybrid fibers and the improvement of the Interfacial Transition Zone (ITZ). The ITZ, is the boundary area between the cement paste and the surface of aggregates, fibers or rebar which plays an important role in permeability, durability and strength of concrete. The microstructures of the ITZ and the cement paste are different and compared to the cement

paste, the ITZ microstructure has more porosity and micro cracks. The thickness of the ITZ depends on parameters such as fiber type, cement type, pozzolan type, etc. [52]. Using nanomaterials and fibers can strengthen the ITZ and improve the mechanical properties of concrete. But on the other hand, with increasing fiber content from 0.2 to 0.25%, the compressive strength decreased slightly. All fibers used were of polymeric materials, which due to high flexibility, can result in fiber balling in the concrete mix at high fiber contents. This phenomenon leads to perforations in the mortar matrix and subsequent internal flaws in interfacial transition zones and thus reduction in GPC compressive strength [53]. From the results obtained, in general, the fiber used had no significant influence on compressive strength of the GPC specimens.

Figure 4: Compressive strength of the FRGPC and control specimens

3.3. TENSILE AND FLEXURAL STRENGTHS

The 7- and 28-day tensile strengths of the FRGPC and control specimens are represented in [Figures 5](#). The lowest 7- and 28- day tensile strength were measured in the control specimen (3.72 and 4.4 MPa, respectively), and the 0.2% hybrid FRGPC specimen (F-0.2) showed the highest 7- and 28-day tensile strengths (4.61 and 5.45 MPa, respectively) among all FRGPC specimens. In the hybrid FRGPC composites, 0.15, 0.2 and 0.25% fiber

content results in approximately 12, 24 and 22% improvement in tensile strengths compared to the control specimen, respectively. The obtained results indicated that using hybrid fibers improved tensile strength values compared to the control specimen and optimal results are achieved at 0.2% fiber content. Further increase in fiber content from 0.2 to 0.25% caused a slight decrease in tensile strength compared to the optimum value (0.2%).

Figure 5: Tensile strength of the FRGPC and control specimens

The 7- and 28-day flexural strengths of the FRGPC and control specimens are illustrated in [Figure 6](#). The 7- and 28-day flexural strengths of the control specimen were 5.82 and 7.11 MPa, respectively. Using 0.15, 0.2 and 0.25% (by volume) of hybrid fibers in GPC mixture, yield to approximately 56, 33 and 51% increase in flexural

strengths compared to the control specimen, respectively. The optimal hybrid fiber content for maximum flexural strength improvement was 0.15%. However, the flexural strength decreases from 0.15 to 0.2% fiber content, and increases from 0.2 to 0.25%. The advantageous effect of fibers on the tensile strength of GPC composites leads to

enhanced ductility characteristics over plain (no fiber) GPC. The polymeric fibers improve the geopolymeric matrix of the composites in terms of formation and/or redistribution of cracks [54]. The basic geopolymer structure includes the formed amorphous geopolymeric gel, residual unreacted raw material particles and varied pores [54-56]. Fibers can offer a bridging effect over the pores or cracks by embedding its two thrums in the cementitious matrix, resulting in increased toughness and strength of the geopolymeric matrix [54]. As a result, higher tensile and flexural strengths were observed in FRGPC specimens than non-fiber ones. On the other

hand, fibers used in this study were hybridized using short and long lengths. Hybridization of fibers in terms of size and type results in the synergistic effect of fibers. The positive synergetic effects of hybridization stems from the different mechanisms of short and long fibers in the GPC matrix. Shorter fibers are more effective against smaller minor cracks, while longer fibers are mainly activated at higher loading scenarios to prevent formation and opening of major cracks. Therefore, the simultaneous usage of different fiber geometries develops positive features in the GPC composite for different levels of exerted loads [38,57].

Figure 6: Flexural strength of the FRGPC and control specimens

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the mechanical and physical properties of GGBFS-based GPC reinforced with hybrid fibers of different volume content (0.15, 0.2 and 0.25%) is investigated. The main results drawn from this study, with regard to its limitations, can be summarized as below:

- 1- Presence of fibers cause reduction of specific density and water absorption of GPC composites, due to micro-structure enhancement and increased density of the matrix. These effects displayed a direct relation with fiber content and independent of fiber type.
- 2- Hybrid fibers improve the compressive strength of GPC due to the reinforcement of the concrete matrix and the improvement of the Interfacial Transition Zone (ITZ).

The increase in compressive strength due to the relatively low modulus and strength of the fibers (compared to steel fibers) was not significant; the hybrid fibers used at optimum content (0.2) increased compressive strength by 6% compared to the non-fiber GPC specimens.

- 3- Due to the crack-bridging mechanism of the fibers, the fiber reinforced GPC composites displayed significant improvement in tensile and flexural strength over unreinforced GPC. Using hybrid fibers at optimum content (0.2% for tensile strength and 0.15% for bending strength), resulted in 24% and 56% increase in tensile and flexural strengths of the GPC specimens compared to non-fiber ones, respectively.

FUNDING/SUPPORT

Not mentioned any Funding/Support by authors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Not mentioned by authors.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author (s) declared no potential conflicts of interests with respect to the authorship and/or publication of this paper.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Davidovits J. Global warming impact on the cement and aggregates industries. *World resource review*. 1994 Apr 4;6(2):263-78. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [2] Part WK, Ramli M, Cheah CB. An overview on the influence of various factors on the properties of geopolymer concrete derived from industrial by-products. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2015 Feb 15;77:370-95. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [3] Yusuf MO, Johari MA, Ahmad ZA, Maslehuddin M. Strength and microstructure of alkali-activated binary blended binder containing palm oil fuel ash and ground blast-furnace slag. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2014 Feb 15;52:504-10. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [4] Phummiphan I, Horpibulsuk S, Rachan R, Arulrajah A, Shen SL, Chindaprasit P. High calcium fly ash geopolymer stabilized lateritic soil and granulated blast furnace slag blends as a pavement base material. *Journal of hazardous materials*. 2018 Jan 5;341:257-67. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [5] Haddad RH, Alshbuol O. Production of geopolymer concrete using natural pozzolan: A parametric study. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2016 Jul 1;114:699-707. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [6] Davidovits J. Geopolymer cement. A review. *Geopolymer Institute, Technical papers*. 2013 Jan;21:1-1. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [7] Hasanbeigi A, Menke C, Price L. The CO₂ abatement cost curve for the Thailand cement industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2010 Nov 1;18(15):1509-18. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [8] Malhotra VM. Reducing CO₂ emissions. *Concrete international*. 2006 Sep 1;28(9):42-5. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [9] Rashad AM. A comprehensive overview about the influence of different additives on the properties of alkali-activated slag—A guide for Civil Engineer. *Construction and building materials*. 2013 Oct 1;47:29-55. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [10] Rao S, Riahi K. The Role of Non-CO₂ Greenhouse Gases in Climate Change Mitigation: Long-term Scenarios for the 21st Century. *The Energy Journal*. 2006 May; 27:177-200. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [11] Chen C, Habert G, Bouzidi Y, Jullien A. Environmental impact of cement production: detail of the different processes and cement plant variability evaluation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2010 Mar 1;18(5):478-85. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [12] McLellan BC, Williams RP, Lay J, Van Riessen A, Corder GD. Costs and carbon emissions for geopolymer pastes in comparison to ordinary portland cement. *Journal of cleaner production*. 2011 Jun 1;19(9-10):1080-90. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [13] Assi LN, Deaver EE, Ziehl P. Effect of source and particle size distribution on the mechanical and microstructural properties of fly Ash-Based geopolymer concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2018 Apr 10;167:372-80. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [14] Amnadnua K, Tangchirapat W, Jaturapitakkul C. Strength, water permeability, and heat evolution of high strength concrete made from the mixture of calcium carbide residue and fly ash. *Materials & Design*. 2013 Oct 1;51:894-901. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [15] Duxson P, Provis JL, Lukey GC, Van Deventer JS. The role of inorganic polymer technology in the development of 'green concrete'. *Cement and Concrete Research*. 2007 Dec 1;37(12):1590-7. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [16] Wang SD, Scrivener KL, Pratt PL. Factors affecting the strength of alkali-activated slag. *Cement and concrete research*. 1994 Jan 1;24(6):1033-43. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [17] Fernández-Jiménez A, García-Lodeiro I, Palomo A. Durability of alkali-activated fly ash cementitious materials. *Journal of Materials Science*. 2007 May 1;42(9):3055-65. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [18] Cheng TW, Chiu JP. Fire-resistant geopolymer produced by granulated blast furnace slag. *Minerals engineering*. 2003 Mar 1;16(3):205-10. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [19] Sarker PK, Kelly S, Yao Z. Effect of fire exposure on cracking, spalling and residual strength of fly ash geopolymer concrete. *Materials & Design*. 2014 Nov 1;63:584-92. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [20] Zhang HY, Kodur V, Qi SL, Cao L, Wu B. Development of metakaolin-fly ash based geopolymers for fire resistance applications. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2014 Mar 31;55:38-45. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [21] Palomo A, Blanco-Varela MT, Granizo ML, Puertas F, Vazquez T, Grutzeck MW. Chemical stability of cementitious materials based on metakaolin. *Cement and Concrete Research*. 1999 Jul 1;29(7):997-1004. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [22] Bakharev T, Sanjayan JG, Cheng YB. Resistance of alkali-activated slag concrete to acid attack. *Cement and Concrete Research*. 2003 Oct 1;33(10):1607-11. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [23] Zhang M, Guo H, El-Korchi T, Zhang G, Tao M. Experimental feasibility study of geopolymer as the next-generation soil stabilizer. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2013 Oct 1;47:1468-78. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [24] Wallah SE. Creep behaviour of fly ash-based geopolymer concrete. *Civil Engineering Dimension*. 2010 Aug 26;12(2):73-8. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [25] De Silva P, Sagoe-Crenstil K, Sirivivatnanon V. Kinetics of geopolymerization: role of Al₂O₃ and SiO₂. *Cement and Concrete Research*. 2007 Apr 1;37(4):512-8. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [26] Neupane K, Chalmers D, Kidd P. High-Strength Geopolymer Concrete- Properties, Advantages and Challenges. *Advances in Materials*. 2018 Jun;7(2):15-25. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [27] Gao K, Lin KL, Wang D, Hwang CL, Tuan BL, Shiu HS, Cheng TW. Effect of nano-SiO₂ on the alkali-activated characteristics of metakaolin-based geopolymers. *Construction and building materials*. 2013 Nov 1;48:441-7. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [28] Petrus HTBM, Hulu J, Dalton GSP, Malinda E, Prakosa RA. Effect of Bentonite Addition on Geopolymer Concrete from Geothermal Silica. *Materials Science Forum*. 2016;841:7-15. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [29] Görhan G, Kürklü G. The influence of the NaOH solution on the properties of the fly ash-based geopolymer mortar cured at different temperatures. *Composites Part B: Engineering*. 2014 Mar;58:371-7. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [30] Davidovits J. Geopolymers: inorganic polymeric new materials. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and calorimetry*. 1991 Aug 1;37(8):1633-56. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [31] Van Jaarsveld JG, Van Deventer JS, Lukey GC. The effect of composition and temperature on the properties of fly ash-and kaolinite-based geopolymers. *Chemical Engineering Journal*. 2002 Oct 28;89(1-3):63-73. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [32] Hardjito D, Wallah SE, Sumajouw DM, Rangan BV. On the development of fly ash-based geopolymer concrete. *Materials Journal*. 2004 Nov 1;101(6):467-72. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).

- [33] Naaman AE, Wongtanakitcharoen T, Hauser G. Influence of Different Fibers on Plastic Shrinkage Cracking of Concrete. *ACI Materials Journal*. 2005;102(1):49-58. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [34] Erdogmus E. Use of fiber-reinforced cements in masonry construction and structural rehabilitation. *Fibers*. 2015 Mar;3(1):41-63. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [35] Soroushian P. Secondary Reinforcement--Adding Cellulose Fibers. *Concrete International*. 1997 Jun 1;19(6):28-34. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [36] Celik A, Yilmaz K, Canpolat O, Al-Mashhadani MM, Aygörmöz Y, Uysal M. High-temperature behavior and mechanical characteristics of boron waste additive metakaolin based geopolymer composites reinforced with synthetic fibers. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2018 Oct 30;187:1190-203. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [37] Al-Majidi MH, Lampropoulos A, Cundy AB. Steel fibre reinforced geopolymer concrete (SFRGC) with improved microstructure and enhanced fibre-matrix interfacial properties. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2017 May 15;139:286-307. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [38] Gao X, Yu QL, Yu R, Brouwers HJ. Evaluation of hybrid steel fiber reinforcement in high performance geopolymer composites. *Materials and Structures*. 2017 Apr 1;50(2):165. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [39] Asrani NP, Murali G, Parthiban K, Surya K, Prakash A, Rathika K, Chandru U. A feasibility of enhancing the impact resistance of hybrid fibrous geopolymer composites: experiments and modelling. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2019 Apr 10;203:56-68. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [40] Alberti MG, Enfedaque A, Gálvez JC, Cánovas MF, Osorio IR. Polyolefin fiber-reinforced concrete enhanced with steel-hooked fibers in low proportions. *Materials & Design*. 2014 Aug 1;60:57-65. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [41] Han TY, Lin WT, Cheng A, Huang R, Huang CC. Influence of polyolefin fibers on the engineering properties of cement-based composites containing silica fume. *Materials & Design*. 2012 May 1;37:569-76. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [42] Deng Z, Shi F, Yin S, Tuladhar R. Characterisation of macro polyolefin fibre reinforcement in concrete through round determinate panel test. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2016;121:229-35. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [43] ASTM International. ASTM C33 / C33M – 18. Standard Specification for Concrete Aggregates [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2018. Available from: <http://astm.org>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [44] ASTM International. ASTM C136 / C136M-14. Standard Test Method for Sieve Analysis of Fine and Coarse Aggregates [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2014. Available from: <http://www.scribd.com> [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [45] ASTM International. ASTM D2419-14. Standard Test Method for Sand Equivalent Value of Soils and Fine Aggregate [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2014. Available from: <https://www.astm.org/Standards/D2419>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [46] British Standards Institution. BS 1881-116:1983. Testing concrete. Method for determination of compressive strength of concrete cubes [Internet]. London; BSI: 1983. Available from: <https://shop.bsigroup.com/ProductDetail/?pid=00000000000049171>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [47] ASTM International. ASTM C496 / C496M-17. Standard Test Method for Splitting Tensile Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2017. Available from: <https://www.astm.org/Standards/C496>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [48] ASTM International. ASTM C293 / C293M-16. Standard Test Method for Flexural Strength of Concrete (Using Simple Beam With Center-Point Loading) [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2016. Available from: <https://www.astm.org/Standards/C293>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [49] ASTM International. ASTM C1018-97. Standard Test Method for Flexural Toughness and First-Crack Strength of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (Using Beam With Third-Point Loading) [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 1997. Available from: <https://www.astm.org/Standards/C1018>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [50] ASTM International. ASTM C642-13. Standard Test Method for Density, Absorption, and Voids in Hardened Concrete [Internet]. West Conshohocken; PA: 2013. Available from: <https://www.astm.org/Standards/C1018>. [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [51] Ganesan N, Abraham R, Raj SD, Sasi D. Fracture Properties of Geopolymer Concrete. *Asian Journal of Civil Engineering (BHRC)*. 2015;16(1):127-34. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [52] Li G. Properties of high-volume fly ash concrete incorporating nano-SiO₂. *Cement and Concrete research*. 2004 Jun 1;34(6):1043-9. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [53] Sukontasukkul P, Pongsopha P, Chindaprasirt P, Songpiriyakij S. Flexural performance and toughness of hybrid steel and polypropylene fibre reinforced geopolymer. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2018 Feb 10;161:37-44. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [54] Zhang ZH, Yao X, Zhu HJ, Hua SD, Chen Y. Preparation and mechanical properties of polypropylene fiber reinforced calcined kaolin-fly ash based geopolymer. *Journal of Central South University of Technology*. 2009 Feb 1;16(1):49-52. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [55] Duxson P, Fernández-Jiménez A, Provis JL, Lukey GC, Palomo A, van Deventer JS. Geopolymer technology: the current state of the art. *Journal of materials science*. 2007 May 1;42(9):2917-33. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [56] Yunsheng Z, Wei S, Zongjin L. Impact behavior and microstructural characteristics of PVA fiber reinforced fly ash-geopolymer boards prepared by extrusion technique. *Journal of materials science*. 2006 May 1;41(10):2787-94. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).
- [57] Grünewald S. Performance-based design of self-compacting fibre reinforced concrete [Doctoral Thesis]. Delft: Delft University of Technology; 2004. [\[View at Google Scholar\]](#) ; [\[View at Publisher\]](#).